

Model diagnostic figure 1 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of All hybrids as a function of genetic distance ($FST_distance$) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto-k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_{loo} : Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_{loo} (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 2 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of All hybrids as a function of genetic distance (Phylogenetic_distance) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto-k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_loo: Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_loo (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 3 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of All hybrids as a function of genetic distance (TCDI) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto-k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_{loo} : Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_{loo} (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 4 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of F1 or F2 hybrids as a function of genetic distance ($FST_distance$) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto- k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO–CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO–CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of $elpd_{loo}$: Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to $elpd_{loo}$ (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 5 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of F1 or F2 hybrids as a function of genetic distance (Phylogenetic_distance) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto- k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of $elpd_{loo}$: Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to $elpd_{loo}$ (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 6 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of F1 or F2 hybrids as a function of genetic distance (TCDI) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto-k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_{loo} : Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_{loo} (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 7 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of Backcross hybrids as a function of genetic distance ($F_{ST_distance}$) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto– k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS–adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO–CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO–CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of $elpd_{loo}$: Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to $elpd_{loo}$ (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 8 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of Backcross hybrids as a function of genetic distance (Phylogenetic_distance) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C.

Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto- k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_{loo} : Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_{loo} (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.

Model diagnostic figure 9 . Diagnostic plots for Hierarchical Bayesian linear model (A–L) assessing model fit, residuals, and convergence for the model predicting proportion of Backcross hybrids as a function of genetic distance (TCDI) geographic distance (mean distance in Km) and Altitudinal distribution dissimilarity [Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance (KSD)] A. Response Distribution: Histogram of observed response values showing zero inflated distribution. B. Residual Distribution: Histogram of model residuals (MAP estimates). Ideally symmetric around zero. C. Residuals vs. Fitted: Pattern checking for heteroscedasticity (red line at $y=0$). Random scatter suggests good fit. D. \hat{R} Values across MCMC samples, values lower than 1.05 indicate good convergence. E. Effective Sample Size (n_{eff}) divided by sample size indicates sampling efficiency for parameters values higher than 0.1 indicate fair sampling. F. Observed vs. Predicted: Posterior predictive check (PPC) showing mean predictions (y_{rep}) vs. actual data (y). Points should cluster around diagonal. G. Mean PPC: Distribution of predicted means vs. observed mean (vertical blue line). Predicted distribution should cover observed value. H. SD PPC: Distribution of predicted SDs vs. observed SD. Checks variance capture. I. Count PPC: For discrete models – compares predicted vs. observed counts. Bars should roughly match indicates reliable performance of hierarchical grouping (random effect when using a frequentist terminology). J. Pareto–k Values: Influential observation diagnostic ($k < 0.7$ ideal, red line shows threshold). Many high values suggest problematic observations. K. ESS-adjusted LOO Reliability: Relative effective sample sizes for LOO-CV. Values around 1 (red line) are preferred validating the use of LOO-CV for assessing model fit. L. MCSE of elpd_{loo} : Monte Carlo error for LOO estimates. Small values relative to elpd_{loo} (red line) difference suggest reliable comparisons.